

Experimental evaluation of a low-power direct air-cooled double-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption prototype

M. Izquierdo^{a,b,*}, J.D. Marcos^c, M.E. Palacios^d, A. González-Gil^{a,b}

^a Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja (CSIC), c/ Serrano Galvache No 4, 28033 Madrid, Spain

^b Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Avenida de la Universidad, No 30, 28914, Leganés, Madrid, Spain

^c Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED), Spain

^d Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Spain

* Corresponding author. Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja (CSIC), c/ Serrano Galvache No 4, 28033 Madrid, Spain. Tel.: +34 91 8713248; fax: +34 91 8713248.

E-mail address: mizquierdo@ietcc.csic.es (M. Izquierdo).

Abstract

This paper describes a new small air-cooled double-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption prototype directly powered by fuel and discusses the experimental findings for some tests carried out in Madrid in 2007, with natural gas as energy source. The prototype, which has been designed to supply 7 kW of cooling power, was able to chill water up to 7-18 °C under extreme outdoor temperatures. A new flat-sheet adiabatic absorber was used allowing it to operate at outdoor temperatures about 45 °C without any sign of crystallization. A mean daily coefficient of performance (COP) of about 1.05 was obtained. Since this absorption machine does not need cooling tower, there is neither water consumption nor *Legionella* pollution. Moreover, it is a quite compact unit. The ratio of cooling power over volume is about 6.0 kW/m³, while for the only air-cooled absorption chiller, Rotartica 045v, in the marked until 2009 this ratio is 4 kW/m³. When comparing with electric chillers presently on the market, this prototype was found to have a cooling cost approximately 15.9% higher and an environmental impact 16.7% lower. The absorption prototype is a more environmentally friendly solution as it does not emit fluorinated refrigerants.

Keywords: Absorption, Double effect, Air-cooled, Adiabatic absorber, Cooling cost, Environmental impact

1. Introduction

Commercial chillers used to air condition buildings operate on either the vapor mechanical compression or the absorption cycle principle. In Spain, residential buildings today are mainly air conditioned by electrically powered mechanical compression chillers, being the air-cooled units the most commonly used. These low-power units are widely used because they are easy to install and comparatively inexpensive. In Madrid, for instance, the installation cost of such a facility to cool an 80-m² home is around €3000 [1]. However, one major drawback of these systems is the high Global Warming Potential (GWP) of refrigerants. For example, in case of using R410A, GWP is 3400 times greater than estimated for CO₂ over a 20-year Integrated Temporal Horizon (ITH), and 1300 times greater over a 100-year ITH, [2].

Lithium bromide water is the system most commonly used in absorption chillers [3]. Encouraging their use for cooling buildings has been a goal of businesses and research centres since the mid-twentieth century. This pursuit is driven by environmental concerns, for the working fluids used by these facilities neither destroy the ozone layer nor contribute directly to the greenhouse effect. Moreover, when powered by renewable or waste heat, they

reduce the indirect greenhouse effect. On those grounds, they can be included in the family of thermally driven chillers, [4]. Apart from liquid absorption cycle, this family includes solid adsorption cycle and steam jet chillers, as well as desiccants (dehumidifiers) and others, as described in Ref. [3]. Such devices share the beneficial environmental characteristics of lithium bromide chillers, as well as other traits such as similar working temperatures and energy efficiency: their heat source must reach temperatures of 70-100 °C while their coefficient of performance (COP), not including the consumption of ancillary equipment, ranges from 0.5 to 0.7.

However, a number of reasons underlie their scant market penetration. Primarily, given their lower energy efficiency than found in electrically powered chillers, they are more costly to run. Furthermore, the ancillary equipment has high electricity consumption, resulting in even lower global efficiency and higher cooling costs. Size is another drawback, as they are larger than mechanical compression chillers. In addition, as cooling towers must be usually installed, a water consumption is generated, and risk of *Legionella* proliferation is associated.

Renewable, solar or other natural or waste heat-powered absorption chillers can be used for domestic cooling, [5] and [6]. The use of such heat sources may lower energy costs, but at a higher initial installation cost. Note that initial investment in “solar cooling” systems can be up to ten times higher than in mechanical compression systems, [7].

For lithium bromide absorption chillers to make headway on the domestic air-conditioning market, to the benefit of the environment, they must be able to compete in cost with electric chillers, consume no water and come in a smaller size. Solar absorption cooling systems will be competitive with electric ones only when absorption chillers can perform as efficiently as mechanical compression chillers. Besides, the initial investment cost of installing a solar facility must be decreased. What is more, the solar facility should be also used for heating purposes.

The Eduardo Torroja Institute for Construction Science, a Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) body, sponsors the “Ahorro de Energía y Reducción de Emisiones en los Edificios” (Energy Saving and Emissions Reduction in Buildings) research group. In 2006 this group set out to build several prototypes of low- power lithium bromide water absorption chillers, capable of competing economically with mechanical compression chillers, an endeavour funded by Spain’s Ministry of Science and Innovation under the INVISO (Industrialization of Sustainable Housing) subproject Sustainable Energy Generation in Housing (Generación Sostenible de Energía en Viviendas). The first was an air-cooled direct-fired double-effect absorption chiller with 7 kW of cooling capacity; the second was a 4.5-kW solar powered single-effect air- cooled absorption chiller; the last one was an air-cooled single- double-effect absorption chiller, driven by solar power, waste heat [8], while operating as a single-effect apparatus or by burning fuel in the double-effect mode.

Development of such prototypes was contingent upon designing, building and testing a new generation absorber, smaller, more readily assembled and with higher mass and heat transfer coefficients than in place to date. This absorber was developed between 2003 and 2006 under research projects DPI 2002-02439 and ENE 2005-08255-CO2-01 with funding from Spain’s Ministry of Industry. Once assembled and tested, the absorber was built into each of the aforementioned prototypes [9]. Note that all of them are direct condensed by air, i.e. re-cooling system is not used. Both absorption and condensation heat are directly transferred from solution to air. These prototypes can work at extreme outdoor temperatures integrated in solar refrigeration or tri-generation systems, without crystallizer the solution.

The work described here focuses on the air-cooled direct-fired double-effect prototype, without addressing their performance in solar cooling or tri-generation systems. Experimental results of trials performed during three characteristics summer days in Madrid are showed. Besides, the corresponding energy costs and the environmental impact are roughly assessed, comparing the obtained results with air-cooled mechanical compression chillers. Note that, to the knowledge of the authors, no direct air-cooled absorption chiller exists on the current market with such characteristics. Even though this study has been made for a low-power chiller, the conclusions drawn from it may be useful for design of medium and high power machines.

2. Electrically powered air-cooled mechanical compression chillers: cooling cost and environmental impact

Air-cooled electrically powered mechanical compression chillers are the type most commonly used to air condition housing. In Spain, according to the Spanish National Statistics Institute [10], the mean standard dwelling has a net area of 80 m² and a maximum cooling load of around 5-7 kW, excluding the kitchen and bathrooms, which are not generally refrigerated. The mean cooling demand in such housing is about 30 kWh/day, but it may climb to 55 kWh/day on very hot days [1]. In the present study, a mean daily demand per dwelling of 30 kWh/day as well as 100 days of refrigeration in Madrid ($Q_{\text{seasonal}} = 3000$ kWh/season) were assumed as a basis to

compare cooling costs and environmental impact between these chillers and the absorption prototype.

2.1. Cooling cost

Without taking into account parameters such as inflation or interest rates, which are difficult to predict in advance, the cost of an air conditioning system may be roughly determined by simply adding the cooling cost to the initial investment. Cooling cost can be found from equations (1) and (2):

$$C_{\text{cold}} = P_{\text{el}} / \text{COP}_{\text{seasonal}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{COP}_{\text{seasonal}} = Q_{\text{seasonal}} / (W_{\text{c}} + W_{\text{ae}})_{\text{seasonal}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{el} is the price of the electricity paid by the user, which in the case of Madrid comes to €0.20 per kWh; Q_{seasonal} represents the seasonal thermal demand and $(W_{\text{c}} + W_{\text{ae}})$ is the seasonal electricity consumed by the compressor and the ancillary equipment.

According to the Spanish Thermal Facility Regulations [11], the seasonal energy efficiency ($\text{COP}_{\text{seasonal}}$) of this kind of chillers is 2.6. Further, Danfoss [12] specifies a nominal performance (COP) for its MTZ050-5 compressor under standard conditions of 2.7, with a margin of error of $\pm 5\%$. However, since this value does not include energy consumption of the ancillary components such as fans and so on, the value for $\text{COP}_{\text{seasonal}}$ would be lower. In a recent paper on electricity consumption of residential air conditioning systems using R410A as refrigerant in Madrid [1], Izquierdo et al. reported a $\text{COP}_{\text{seasonal}}$ of 2.4. In light of those results, the $\text{COP}_{\text{seasonal}}$ value adopted in this paper was 2.4.

Further to Eq. (1), cooling cost in this case would be €0.083 per kWh, resulting the mean daily cost of electricity €2.50. In as much as the air conditioning season in Madrid lasts approximately 100 days, the seasonal cost of electricity for air conditioning would be around €250. The initial investment in these air conditioners is approximately €3000.

2.2. Environmental impact

Air-cooled chillers require no water and therefore they do not breed *Legionella*. In addition, according to the Montreal Protocol, the refrigerant used does not destroy the ozone layer. However, it presents a high GWP effect. For instance, in the case of R410A, which is one of the most commonly used refrigerants in this kind of systems, this effect is 3400 times greater than estimated for CO₂ over a 20-year ITH, and 1300 times greater over a 100-year ITH, [2]. Notwithstanding, in order to compute the environmental impact of the whole system, it is also necessary to take into account emissions associated to electricity consumption. The parameter used for this purpose is the Total Equivalent Warming Impact (TEWI), which represents the amount of equivalent CO₂ emissions.

TEWI consist of two different parameters: The first, GWP, takes account of the refrigerant that leaks directly into the air, while the second, IGWP (Indirect Global Warming Potential), refers to emissions attributable to generation of the electricity needed to power air conditioning systems.

According to Refs. [13,14], the Direct Global Warming Potential (DGWP) can be calculated from Eq. (3), where GWP represents the Global Warming Potential effect of the refrigerant compared with CO₂, f is the yearly leakage rate (%), M_{R} is the refrigerant mass in the chiller (kg) and N represents its lifespan in years.

$$\text{DGWP} = \text{GWP} \cdot f \cdot M_{\text{R}} \cdot N \quad (3)$$

These facilities may be assumed to have a lifespan of 20 years and the refrigerant load to come to approximately 2 kg. On the other hand, the leakage rate f is difficult to define because each facility has its own design and operating characteristics and no compulsory maintenance program is presently in place. Some public bodies have published data in this regard, however. The Japanese Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI), for instance, computed fluorinated refrigerant leaks in 2008 in that country to be ten times higher than forecast in 2007 [15]. One of the reasons for the erroneous estimate may have been an underestimation of the amount of refrigerant discharged during equipment breakdown and repair. The annual leakage rate for household room air conditioners was revised upwards from 0.2% in 2007 to 2% in 2008; for chilling units from 2 to 6% and for medium-sized refrigeration units from 1.1 to 17%.

Determination of the percentage of refrigerant that leaks from the time it is loaded in the chiller until the unit is dismantled at the end of its service life is, then, subject to a number of practical difficulties. It is also difficult

to ascertain how leaks are calculated in the refrigerant banks referred to in the F-gas Regulation 842/2006/ EC. This difficulty is even greater in the case of R410A for which no specific data on emissions were found, yet. Moreover, this figure may be high given the high operating pressure used with this gas.

The assumptions adopted in light of the foregoing, all deemed conservative, were as follows:

1. All the refrigerant (2 kg) leaks out of the unit between 1st and 15th year.
2. The chiller is recharged in year 15 (2 kg).
3. Half of the refrigerant (1 kg) leaks into the atmosphere from year 15 to year 20.
4. In year 20, at the end of the unit service life, 25% of the full charge (0.5 kg) is recovered and stored in refrigerant banks as per the F-gas Regulation.

Further to these assumptions, 3.5 kg of refrigerant would leak into the atmosphere over 20 years, i.e., at a rate of 0.175 kg or 5.0% per year, which is consistent with the findings published by the METI. Assuming R410A is the refrigerant used and ITH coincide with the service life of the chiller, the carbon dioxide equivalent due to refrigerant leakage (DGWP) would be approximately 595 kg per year.

IGWP represents the amount of CO₂ emitted to the atmosphere in generating the electricity consumed by the chiller. Taking into account the emission of CO₂ per kWh of electricity generated in Spain was 0.4 kg in 2008 [16] and the mean electricity consumption during cooling season is about 1250 kWh, a total of 500 kg of CO₂ are emitted per dwelling per year. Consequently, the TEWI would be 1095 kg of carbon dioxide equivalent per year.

3. Air-cooled direct-fired double-effect absorption chiller prototype

3.1. Background

The most efficient absorption chillers presently on the market are water-cooled lithium bromide double-effect devices. These systems typically use a cooling tower that consumes water, a precious commodity in places on the planet where the climate makes air-conditioning an imperative. Furthermore, it fosters *Legionella* proliferation. The ancillary absorption apparatus includes the solution pump and the pumps for external fluids feeding the evaporator, generator or condenser-absorber, as well as the cooling tower fan. This ancillary equipment in water-cooled absorption chillers is generally acknowledged to have higher electricity consumption than other electrically driven chillers. Moreover, absorption chillers are larger and more costly than electric devices. Their considerable size can be attributed to the absorber, a component that has undergone no important material change in the last 50 years. According to state of the art values, these chillers operate at a thermal COP of 1.0-1.3, depending on the condensation temperature. However, these efficiency values decline to about 0.75 when electric consumption of the ancillary equipment is factored and COP is referred to primary energy. Nevertheless, the efficiency of double-effect chillers is much closer to the efficiency of air-cooled electric chillers than that one of single-effect units.

The environmental benefits of lithium bromide chillers have encouraged researchers to seek new solutions, since if some of the aforementioned problems could be solved, these chillers might be in the future an alternative to electric chillers. The challenge is to develop a high efficiency air-cooled chiller using an absorber and a condenser able to operate at extreme outdoor temperatures, inexpensive, easy to build, small sized and with no water consumption. In this regard, the authors have designed and built an air-cooled direct-fired double-effect absorption prototype that uses fuel as an energy source. Next, a description of the prototype and some of the experimental results are shown.

3.2. Flat-sheet adiabatic absorber

The falling film type absorbers presently used in lithium bromide absorption chillers are characterized by a number of problems: low mass transfer, low heat transfer and large volume, as stated by [17]. On the other hand, the adiabatic spray absorber developed and patented by Ryan as a solution [18], is not itself free of drawbacks. According to its inventor [19], these include:

1. Low liquid flow rate, calling for many spraying units. As a result, the absorber occupies a great deal of space.

2. Variable droplet diameter.
3. Diameter of a significant proportion of droplets is under 150 μm . As a result, a substantial portion of the mass flow is of no use for absorption purposes.
4. Considerable head loss and high power demand in the pump driving the solution.

In an attempt to solve these problems, Warnakulasuriya and Worek [20] developed a spray absorber with 400- μm diameter droplets. This device delivered higher mass transfer than Ryan's spray and multiplied the performance of commercial falling film absorbers by about four-fold.

Tackling the problem from a different angle, the authors of the present work modified the spray absorber, first by building a parallel droplet spray absorber, patented in Spain, able to generate droplets with no pressure drop and diameters of over 300 μm , [21] This absorber was not commercially viable because the mass of the solution was difficult to control and the mass transfer coefficient was similar to Ryan's. A jet absorber subsequently designed and built, also featuring no pressure drop, improved mass transfer but solution mass remained uncontrolled [22]. The next step was to develop a flat-sheet absorber resting on a slanted surface that was published by [23], able to operate at a higher flow rate and therefore greater mass transfer. While it was also readily controlled, the need for material support constituted yet another difficulty. To solve these problems, two new adiabatic absorbers were studied by Palacios et al.: one generating a cone-shaped sheet [24,25] and other a flat-fan-shaped sheet with an oval nozzle [26], Fig. 1. The conclusions drawn from [25] show that the mass transfer coefficient delivered by the flat-sheet spray was five times greater than by the Warnakulasuriya and Worek proposal. This improvement in mass transfer constituted, therefore, a significant development in absorber technology.

Fig. 1. Flat-fan-shaped sheet.

Izquierdo et al. have patented this flat-fan sheet adiabatic absorber [27]. It comprises a tank to store the diluted solution, a bank of flat-fan sheet sprayers, a solution pump and an air-cooling system to refrigerate directly the solution.

Through two sprayers, the storage tank collects concentrated solution coming from the low and high generators. In this process, the strong solution absorbs a considerable amount of the vapor generated in the evaporator and consequently gets warmer. In order to remove this absorption heat, a solution air-cooler was assembled. As represented in Fig. 2, this cooling system is formed by a recirculation solution pump, a finned air heat exchanger and a fan. The diluted warmed solution is pumped through the solution-air heat exchanger (HEX), where it is cooled directly by the outdoor air. Once cooled, it returns to the absorber storage tank through a few of sprayers contributing to the vapor absorption process. Lastly, part of the solution in the tank is pumped again to the generator completing the LiBr/H₂O solution cycle.

Fig. 2. Adiabatic absorber schema.

This arrangement increases both the mass transfer coefficient and the area available for mass transfer, significantly reducing volume. Moreover, since the flow rate is higher in sheet than in droplet sprays, absorber volume can be reduced even further. The process is readily controlled and pressure drop is small, see [25].

As an adiabatic unit, it transfers mass and heat separately as the absorber of Ryan. Its operation involves pumping the solution from the absorber to the high and low-temperature generators in the double-effect prototype. Similarly, the solution is pumped from the absorber and recirculated in a heat exchanger, where the absorption heat is transferred either to the outside air or to the water from a cooling tower. This characteristic affords this new generation of absorbers with a greater heat transfer in a smaller exchange area. They are more efficient than Ryan or Warnakulasuriya and Worek's absorbers and, as far as known, also than any commercial absorber in use today.

3.3. Prototype description

Fig. 3 shows the flow chart of the air-cooled direct-fired double-effect lithium bromide absorption prototype, in parallel flow. The energy source is fuel and the solution is heated by direct combustion. The system needs no cooling tower, water or pump for the external fluid in the generator. By contrast, it includes a flat-sheet adiabatic absorber.

Fig. 3. Flow chart of the air-cooled direct-fired double-effect lithium bromide absorption chiller.

The system essentially consists of the following components: a high-temperature generator (HG) with a burner (Q); a direct air-cooled adiabatic absorber (A); a direct air-cooled condenser (C); an evaporator (E); a low-temperature generator (LG); high- and low- temperature recoverers (HR and LR); a coolant sub-cooler (SC); a solution pump to power generators (SP); recirculation solution pump (RSP); solution-air finned heat exchanger (HEX); low- and high- pressure expansion valves (LEV and HEV); a variable speed fan (F); a external evaporator fluid pump (EEFP); vacuum system; measurement and control systems (P, T, F).

The absorber assembly, which separates mass and heat transfer processes, comprises a tank to store the diluted solution, a bank of sheet sprayers, the recirculation solution pump, the finned heat exchanger, the fan and the solution pump. The storage tank collects the solution from the sprayers and feeds the two solution pumps. In order to remove the absorption heat, the diluted solution is pumped to the HEX by the RSP. The outdoor air is drawn in the heat exchanger by the variable speed fan. Once cooled, the solution returns to the sprayers (19) and continues the absorption cycle. The concentrated solution from the HG and the LG (14 and 16) is driven to the absorber through two other sprayers.

The water vapor formed in the LG (1B) pass through a droplet separator and then it is condensed in a finned heat exchanger, C. The condensing fluid is the outdoor air, which had previously cooled the solution in the absorber. The prototype is designed in such a way that with only a fan it is possible to cool the absorber, the condenser and the sub-cooler at the same time. Once condensed, the coolant is driven to the evaporator through the LEV. The evaporator assembly includes a tank, a liquid coolant distributor, a falling film heat exchanger and a pump that drives the chilled water to the air-conditioned space. Both the HEV and the LEV feed the liquid coolant distributor. One of the advantages of this evaporator is that it can be easily dismantled for inspection and maintenance.

The HG consists of a modulating burner, an exchanger that transfers heat from the combustion gases to the lithium bromide solution and a water vapor separator. The modulating burner can be fired by a fossil fuel, preferably natural gas, or by renewable fuels such as biodiesel, bio-ethanol or biomass. The heat exchanger efficiency varies from 80% to 90%, depending on the solution boiling temperature. The diluted solution (11) absorbs heat from the combustion gases, boils and produces superheated vapor. Steam is separated from the solution in a high-temperature separator, being ready for use as a heat source in the low-temperature generator. The concentrated solution (12) returns to the absorber through the HR. Exhaust gases are collected in a chimney that releases them into the atmosphere.

The low-temperature generator is a plate heat exchanger. The water vapor coming from the HG (1A) circulates in the hot side of the heat exchanger, while the diluted solution (8) flows on the other side. The steam, i.e., the coolant, condenses and the liquid water (1CA) is driven to the sub-cooler. In the LG, the water latent heat is transferred to diluted solution, which is heated up to the boiling temperature. A new coolant (water vapor) is then released and driven to the condenser. The solution is concentrated (9) and returns to the absorber through the LR. The SP feeds diluted solution from the absorber (5) to the HG and LG, through the HR and LR, respectively. The flow is split in the distribution valve (V1) to feed both generators (7, 10)

The HR and LR are plate heat exchangers where concentrated solution flowing out of HG (12) and LG (9), respectively, transfers heat to diluted solution from the absorber (10 and 7). Consequently, the diluted solution is preheated before entering the generators (11 and 8) and the concentrated solution is cooled, to the benefit of absorption process and energy efficiency.

The SC has two components, an aluminium finned tube heat exchanger and a fan. The coolant that had been condensed in the low-temperature generator (1CA) is driven to this heat exchanger, where it is cooled at a temperature slightly higher than the outdoors air temperature. Then the coolant is driven to the HEV.

Experiments consisted of chilling water from a non-insulated 1000-l tank exposed to the outdoor temperature. The external fluid pump (EFEP in Fig. 3) pumped water from the tank to the prototype's evaporator, where it was chilled. After that, it returned to the tank being mixed with the remaining water. Measurements of water temperature were taken in the tank as well as at the evaporator outlet. The water flow rate was also registered.

Finally, Fig. 4 shows a photograph of the prototype. Note that it is rather compact, with a total volume of about 1.2 m³, including the chimney.

3.4. *Experimental results and discussion*

The double-effect prototype was tested from 1 August to middle October 2007 in Madrid. Whereas most of the tests were carried out at natural outdoor air temperatures, in the end of the testing period experiments were run with artificial air temperatures, i.e. with temperatures generated inside a climatic chamber where the prototype was placed. Experimental sessions generally started about 11:00 h and finished between 18:00 h and 21:00 h,

depending on weather conditions. Twelve experiments were carried out, which completed about 100 hours of prototype operation. However, not all of them were properly registered. All the experiments were handily controlled. Following, experimental results corresponding to three different days are presented and discussed, showing the achieved progress and the points to be improved.

Fig. 4. Air-cooled direct-fired double-effect lithium bromide absorption prototype.

Figs. 5-22 show some of the experimental findings for two summer days in 2007, 1 and 8 August, working with natural outdoor temperatures. Figs. 23 and 24 contain some of the experimental results for an outdoor temperature profile artificially generated in a climatic chamber on 4 September.

3.4.1. Results obtained during a very hot day (1 August 2007)

Fig. 5 shows the characteristic temperatures recorded during this experiment, which began at 11:10 h and concluded at approximately 18:50 h. The outdoor temperature reached a high of 40 °C between 15:50 h and 18:00 h. The water temperature in the tank, which initially was 27 °C, was lowered to 16 °C at 16:35 h and to 12.5 °C at 19:55 h, when the outdoor temperature was 36.5 °C.

Fig. 5. Temperatures on a very hot day (1 August 2010).

The chilled water temperature, i.e. temperature at the evaporator outlet, was 27 °C at 11:15 h and declined to 14.5 °C at 16:30 h, reaching 10.5 °C at 19:55 h. The temperature of the air at the absorber-condenser outlet peaked at 47 °C at 17:40 h, and declined to 42 °C at 19:40 h, when the burner was disconnected. The water temperature dropped to 10.5 °C when the outdoor temperature was 36.5 °C thanks to the inertia in the prototype.

In Fig. 5, the difference of temperatures, $\Delta t = t_{out} - t_{chwi}$, has been represented as a manner to value the cooling effect with respect to the outdoor temperature. Between 15:00 h and 20:00 h, when the outdoor temperature (t_{out}) was at its highest, the difference between outdoor temperature and chilled water temperature (t_{chwi}), Δt , held steady at around 25 °C. This parameter is comparable to that one obtained with air-cooled conventional machines for the same weather conditions.

Both condensation and absorption temperatures are shown in Fig. 6. The final absorption temperature peaked at 48 °C between 15:30 h and 18:20 h, while the condensation temperature during that interval was about 52 °C. It is interesting to see that the final absorption temperature was about 7 °C higher and the condensation temperature about 11 °C higher than the outdoor temperature. These results confirm the high efficiency of both the air-solution heat exchanger in the absorber and the air-cooled condenser.

Fig. 6. Variation in absorption-condensation temperatures (1 August 2007).

Fig. 7 shows solution temperatures at the inlet and outlet of the high-temperature generator. At the beginning of the experiment, the outlet temperature was about 142 °C, but it reached 155 °C at 13:00 h approximately. The range was observed to narrow in the rest of the experiment, fluctuating from 151 °C to 154 °C. The flow rate remained nearly constant at 0.032 kg/s. Note that the prototype became operational 20 min after start-up and no signs of crystallization were detected at any time during the trial.

Fig. 7. Solution temperatures in the high-temperature generator (1 August 2007).

The heating power delivered to the high-temperature generator is shown in Fig.8. As seen, the input power was initially 3 kW but it increases steadily throughout the experiment to 4.4 kW, which was reached at 19:15 h.

Fig. 8. Heating power delivered to the high-temperature generator (1 August 2007).

As shown in Fig. 9, absolute pressure in the high generator ranged between 1.15 and 1.4 bar. The pressure corresponding to the low generator, which was also plotted in Fig. 9, varied between 100 and 140 mbar.

Fig. 9. Pressures in high and low generators (1 August 2007).

Cooling capacity, as shown in Fig.10, ranged from 4 kW at start-up to a maximum of 53 kW at 19:40 h. The chilled water flowed across the evaporator at a rate of 0.59 kg/s. Between 17:00 h and 19:00 h, when the outdoor temperature was about 40°C, the mean cooling capacity was about 4.5 kW, which approximately represents 65% of the nominal capacity. As noted earlier, the prototype responded very rapidly, with cooling beginning just 20 min after burner start-up. Moreover, refrigeration continued some minutes after turning off the burner, due to the inertia accumulated in the prototype. That is, when the remaining refrigerant in the condenser reaches the evaporator through the expansion valve, it is able to produce cooling effect during a few additional minutes.

Fig. 11 shows the thermal COP expressed as the ratio between the effect of the evaporator (cooling power) and the heat supplied to the high-temperature generator. The values ranged between 1.1 and 1.4 most of the experiment. Note the peaks reached at the end of the experiment are due to the aforementioned inertia effect. Taking into account that the cooling effect during the whole day was 38.7 kWh and the amount of energy absorbed by the solution was 32.2, the daily COP reached a value of about 1.2.

Fig. 10. Cooling power generated in the evaporator (1 August 2007).

Fig. 11. Thermal daily COP (1 August 2007).

Electricity consumed by the ancillary equipment during the whole experiment was 6.8 kWh. According to Eq. (4), the mean daily COP dipped to 0.99 when the consumption of ancillary components (W_{aux}) was included in the calculations. Likewise, the daily COP adopted a value of 0.77 when calculated in terms of primary energy according to Eq. (5), where $\eta_{cp} = 0.38$ is the mean efficiency of the Spanish power plants. Fig.12 presents the values of COP_{aux} and COP_{prim} during the whole experiment.

$$COP_{aux} = \frac{Q_e}{Q_g + W_{aux}} \quad (4)$$

$$COP_{prim} = \frac{Q_e}{Q_g + \frac{W_{aux}}{\eta_{cp}}} \quad (5)$$

Fig.13 shows the Dühring diagram for the solution in the high- and low-temperature generators at 18:00 h., including the pressure drop. The high-temperature generator increased the concentration from 56% to 59.5%, whereas in the low-temperature generator outlet concentration was only 58%. This is an indication that the low-temperature generator is not optimized yet.

Fig. 12. COP including electricity consumption and in terms of primary energy (1 August 2007).

Fig. 13. Dühring diagram (1 August 2007 at 6:00 p.m.)

3.4.2. Results obtained during a hot day (8 August 2007)

Fig. 14 shows the temperature of the chilled water and the air during the experiment carried out on 8 August 2007.

The experiment began at about 10:45 h and concluded at 17:50 h. Initially, the outdoor air temperature was 24 °C and peaked at 33 °C between 16:00 h and 17:30 h, declining to 30 °C at 5:50 p.m. The temperature of the water in the tank, which at 11:00 h was 23 °C, dropped to 8.5 °C at 14:30 h. when the temperature of the chilled water leaving the evaporator was 7 °C. Two power outages were registered, at 14:45 h and 15:20 h, during which operation of the burner as well as the rest of the facility was interrupted for 15 min and 10 min, respectively. Consequently, cooling was suspended and temperature of the water in the tank increases to 12 °C. When cooling resumed at 15:30 h, the tank temperature declined to 12 °C and the temperature of the water leaving the evaporator dipped to a new low of 10.5 °C.

The condensation and final absorption temperatures are shown in Fig. 15. The absorption temperature peaked at 42 °C 17:20 h, while the condensation temperature was about 46 °C. Thus, it can be said that the final absorption temperature was 8 °C higher and the condensation temperature 12 °C higher than the outdoor temperature.

As seen in Fig. 16, solution temperature in the high-generator rose from an initial value of 140-65 °C at 14:50 h. When operation was restored after the electric power outage, the temperature climbed to 160 °C at 15:45 h and

reached 168 °C at 17:20 h, when the heating power was disconnected. The solution was not observed to crystallize at any time.

Fig.14. Temperatures on a hot day (8 August 2007)

Fig.15. Variation in absorption-condensation temperatures (8 August 2007).

Fig. 16. Temperature of the solution in the high-temperature generator (8 August 2007).

Figures from 17-19 show the heating power delivered to the high-temperature generator, the pressure in both generators and the cooling effect in the evaporator, respectively.

Fig.17. Heating power supplied to the high-temperature generator (8 August 2007).

Fig.18. Pressures in high and low generators (8 August 2007)

Fig.19. Cooling power generated in the evaporator (8 August 2007).

The cooling power delivered during the experiment was approximately 21.0 kWh, while 21.0 kWh was the amount of heat absorbed by the solution. The electricity consumed by the ancillaries during the whole experiment was 5.1 kWh. The mean thermal COP, deducting the electrical outage time, came to 1.0 and dipped to 0.80 when the consumption of ancillary components was included in the calculations. When computed in terms of primary energy (Eq. (5)), it adopted a value of 0.61. The variation of COP throughout the experiment can be seen in Figs. 20 and 21.

Fig.20. Thermal daily COP (8 August 2007).

Fig.21. COP including electric electricity consumption and in terms of primary energy (8 August 2007)

Fig. 22 shows the Duhring diagram at 16:30 h., when the Lithium bromide concentration was 57% in the absorber and 63 % at the generator outlet. As in the very hot day experiment, concentration raised less (to 60%) in the low than in the high-temperature generator.

Fig. 22. Dühring diagram (8 August 2007 at 4:30 p.m).

3.4.3. Results obtained during a day with artificial temperature distribution (4th September 2007)

On 4 September 2007, the outdoor temperature was generated artificially in a climatic chamber. In order to achieve extreme working conditions, the absorber and condenser were cooled with the air in the chamber. The high artificial temperature was about 44.5 °C, whereas the high natural temperature was 32 °C (Fig. 23).

Fig. 23. Distribution of characteristic temperatures (4 September 2007).

The experiment began at 11:15 h at a temperature of 29 °C, which increase gradually to 38 °C at 15:00 h, where it plateaued until 16:20 h. Between 16:20 h and 16:40 h it climbed to 42 °C, where it steadied until 17:15 h, to finally rise to 44.5°C, approximately. The initial temperature of the air at the absorber and condenser outlet, 35 °C. climbed to 50 °C by the end of the experiment, being the maximum condensation temperature reached about 54 °C. The variation in the air temperature at the absorber-condenser outlet was found to be contingent upon the fan speed control system, which operated at a variable flow rate. This effect was confined by raising the fan speed between 14:45 h and 16:30 h, when the cooling air outlet temperature decreased in about four degrees. Fig. 23 also shows the real outdoor temperature measured at a weather station in the experimental plant. It was 22 °C at 11:00 h and

kept roughly constant at 31 °C from 16:00 h to the end of the experiment.

Water in the tank was cooled from 25 °C to 20 °C, while the lowest chilled water temperature was about 18 °C, attained at 16:35 h. and 17:40 h. Note that during this period of time, the artificial outdoor temperature raised from 38 °C to 44 °C. The experiment concluded at 18:15 h.

Fig. 24 shows the temperature of the solution in the high- temperature generator. After start-up, the solution reached 165°C, increasing up to 180 °C at about 13.30 h. Then, the temperature followed the pattern established for the experiment, remaining more or less stable during the rest of the experiment. One of the most interesting conclusions drawn from this experiment is that despite the high temperatures of the solution, with differences between the inlet and outlet about 20 °C, no signs of crystallization were observed.

Fig. 24. Temperature of the solution in the high generator (4 September 2007)

The cooling effect during the whole experiment was about 20 kWh, being the mass flow rate of the chilled water 0.331/s. As the total amount of heat supplied to the high-generator was about 21 kWh, the mean daily COP was 0.95. The mean cooling power was 2.9 kW and the total electricity consumption 5.5 kWh.

3.5. Uncertainty analysis

In this section, uncertainty is analyzed and summarized according to Marcos [5]. The data acquisition equipment used in this work consisted of PT100 thermoresistances, pressure transducers and mass flow meters, whose accuracy were respectively ± 0.1 K, $\pm 0.25\%$ and 1-3%. Besides, a DC-100 acquisition system registered all the measurements with an accuracy of 0.05%. Taking into account error propagation, uncertainty in calculated parameters is the following: ± 8.1 for cooling power, $\pm 6.1\%$ for heating capacity and $\pm 9.5\%$ for COP.

4. Absorption prototype: cooling cost and environmental impact

4.1. Cooling cost

This section evaluates the cost of air conditioning the same dwelling as analyzed in section 2 with an air-cooled direct-fired double-effect absorption chiller. The data used for this analysis are taken from the experimental results described above, even though the prototype had not yet been optimized when the tests were conducted. The natural gas used for domestic heating and hot water was considered as energy source. The assumed price was €0.05/kWh, which, including all items and tax, was the corresponding cost of domestic natural gas in Madrid during the summer of 2007.

Following the method exposed in section 2, the cooling cost was obtained by adding the cost of the natural gas burnt to drive the absorption chiller and the cost of the electricity consumed by the ancillaries.

On 1 August, the mean combustion efficiency was about 90%, being the daily consumption of natural gas

35.8 kWh. The total cooling effect had been 38.7 kWh, while the electricity consumption had come to 6.8 kWh. Thus, the cost per day was €1.79 for natural gas and €136 for electricity, bringing the total daily cost to €3.15. The cost per kWh of cooling effect resulted to be €0.081/kWh.

On 8 August, when the mean combustion efficiency was 88%, the daily consumptions were 23.9 kWh for natural gas and 5.1 kWh for electricity, while the cooling capacity was 21 kWh. As a result, the daily cost of energy consumption was €1.19 for natural gas and €1.02 for electricity. The total daily cost came to €2.21 and the cost per kWh of cooling effect to €0.105.

On 4 September, the mean combustion efficiency was 85%, being the daily consumption of natural gas 24.7 kWh and of electricity 5.5 kWh, while the cooling capacity had been 20 kWh. The cost of natural gas resulted to be €124/day and of electricity €1.10/day, bringing the total daily cost to €2.34 and the cost per kWh of cooling capacity to €0.117.

Taking the three days together, the total cost of energy to deliver 79.7 kWh of cooling power was €7.70. Therefore, the mean cooling cost was €0.097/kWh. Comparing with electrically powered chillers, the cost of cooling has found to be 15.9% higher. Regarding to electricity consumption, it came to 17.4 kWh, which means 0.22 kWh and €0.0437 per kWh of cooling effect. The total of natural gas burned was 84.3 kWh and the corresponding cost came to €422, which implies €0.0529 per kWh of cooling effect. The initial investment to build this prototype was about €20000, excluding research costs. This sum is obviously not comparable to the initial investment needed for a commercial chiller.

4.2. Environmental impact

Since air-cooled chillers require no water, they entail no risk of *Legionella* pollution. Besides, as the refrigerant is water, it does not destroy the ozone layer. While water vapor is the gas with the most powerful warming impact, when it leaks out of the machine it returns to the atmosphere without generating any additional impact, i.e., its GWP is zero.

The mean thermal COP for the three analyzed days was 1.05. Assuming this value as a seasonal COP for the 100 summer days with a mean cooling demand of 30 kWh, the amount of natural gas consumed per season will come to 3242 kWh, if the mean combustion efficiency is considered to be 88%. According to the major natural gas distribution company in Spain, Gas Natural, (28), when burning a kWh of this fuel 0.2 kg of CO₂ is emitted to the atmosphere. Assuming this value, 648 kg of CO₂ will be emitted.

In addition, the ancillaries consume a mean 0.22 kWh of electricity per kWh of cooling effect. Extrapolating this to the entire summer, the electricity consumed per day would come to 660 kWh. Following assumptions made in section 2, the IGWP associated to this consumption will be 264 kg of CO₂ per season. Thus, the total global warming emissions will be about 912 kg of equivalent CO₂, which compared with electric chillers, implies about 16.7% of reduction (183 kg of CO₂ per year). Note that emission of 595 kg of CO₂ will be avoided by year in form of HFC refrigerant.

5. Conclusions

Air-cooled, electrically powered mechanical compression chillers, which cool the air inexpensively and feature low installation and maintenance costs, are the type most commonly used today to air condition housing. The lithium bromide absorption chillers sold commercially, in turn, are either single-effect units or water-cooled double-effect facilities. No air-cooled single- or double-effect chillers are available on the market.

The conclusions drawn from the experiments carried out with an air-cooled direct-fired double-effect lithium bromide absorption prototype are set out below:

- A new flat-sheet adiabatic absorber directly cooled by air proved to be able to operate in very high outdoor temperatures. This absorber was installed in a prototype with 7 kW of nominal cooling capacity, which was able to chill water between 7 °C and 18 °C in extreme outdoor temperatures obtaining a mean daily COP of about 1.05. Even under these conditions, the solution did not crystallize.
- Moreover, it is a quite compact unit: the nominal ratio of cooling power over volume is about 6.0 kW/m³, while for the only commercial air-cooled absorption chiller this ratio is 4 kW/m³.
- Since this absorption machine does not need cooling tower, there is neither water consumption nor

Legionella pollution.

- This prototype can be powered by the same kind of fuel as used for domestic heating and hot water. When using natural gas as a source of heat, emissions of equivalent CO_2 are higher than for an electrically powered air-cooled chiller. However, taking into account the nature of refrigerants, the prototype proved to be more environmentally friendly because the absence of fluorinated refrigerant (HFC) emissions reduced the overall figure by approximately 16.7%.
- Prior to optimization, this prototype had a cooling cost around 15.9% higher than the electrically powered air conditioners presently available on the market. This is due to the high electricity consumption corresponding to the ancillary equipment, which is in the same order as the cost of the driving natural gas. This fact makes necessary an energy optimization of the prototype, mainly focused on the low-temperature generator, the evaporator and the consumption of the ancillary equipment. In order to carry out this optimization, the authors have decided to build a new lithium bromide absorption prototype that combines into a single unit both single- and double-effect operation modes. In this way, not only the efficiency of the chiller may be improved, but also the ratio of cooling capacity over size may be raised up to 10.

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